

VISCOELASTIC RESPONSE OF TIRE CORD - RUBBER COMPOSITES

N.J. Ballintyn

and

R.B. Pipes

University of Delaware
Newark, DE

Previous research concerning the viscoelastic behavior of fiber reinforced composite materials has usually addressed or assumed the concept of an elastic fiber reinforcing a viscoelastic matrix. In addition, the experimental interrelation of relaxation and complex properties is seldom approached even though the analytical methods are, of course, available.

The objective of the work reported herein is three fold. It includes the development of an analytical model which uses constituent properties in predicting the response of a fiber reinforced composite in which both the fiber and the matrix exhibit viscoelastic behavior. The correlation between the relaxation and complex properties of a composite consisting of viscoelastic phases is also investigated. Experimental characterization of the time-dependent and dynamic properties of tire materials, namely polyester and Kevlar cord, "as-Processed" rubber and the cord reinforced rubber composite has been performed as well.

The analysis begins with the derivation of the effective elastic modulus in terms of the phase properties. This follows a method similar to that given by Hashin (1972). It results in an expression like the one found by Hill (1964) as well as the one describing the cylinder assemblage model of Hashin and Rosen (1964). Assigning an exponential series form to the phase relaxation moduli and using the LaPlace Transform as required for the correspondence principle, the effective relaxation modulus of the lamina is developed.

In order to provide experimental support for the analytical model, the following approach is taken. Tensile relaxation tests of the cord materials, the rubber and a unidirectional lamina of the composite are performed. Measurements are also made of the complex moduli of the constituents and the composite using tensile dynamic tests covering an extended range of frequencies. Using a collocation method the data is inserted into the exponential series representation of the phase moduli. Linear viscoelastic transformations are then utilized to show the interrelation of the relaxation and complex moduli.

In addition to the experimental substantiation of the analysis the relaxation and dynamic test results for both cord types, the "as-processed" rubber and the unidirectional composite are presented.